

**MESOSPHERIC TEMPERATURE INVERSION OVER BAHIR DAR REGION
(11°N/37°E), ETHIOPIA USING SABER SATELLITE DATA**

A GRADUATE THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES OF
BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY

IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIRMENTES FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTER
OF SCIENCE IN PHYSICS

BY

SILABAT ESHETIE

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BAHIR DAR ETHIOPIA

JUNE 2018

CERTIFICATION

The undersigned hereby certify that they have read and recommend to the school of postgraduate studies for the acceptance of this project work entitled: **"MESOSPHERIC TEMPERATURE INVERSION OVER BAHIR DAR"** by **SILABAT ESHETIE** in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of **MASTER OF SCIENCE IN PHYSICS** at Bahir Dar University.

Date: JUNE 2018.....

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